

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Cyclopentanone, Cyclohexanone and 2-Methylcyclohexanone by 2,6-Dichlorophenol Indophenol in Aqueous Alkaline Medium. Part-I

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Kinetics of oxidation of cyclic ketones by 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol have been investigated spectrophotometrically in presence of alkali. The reaction shows first order with respect to cyclic ketone and second order with respect to 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol. The rate increases linearly with the alkali concentration. The final reaction product, i.e. leuco-dye does not affect the rate. Similarly, the addition of neutral electrolytes also does not influence the rate. The activation parameters have been calculated and a plausible reaction path has been set out.

DURING recent years oxidation-reduction reactions involving the transfer of an electron between the reactants have been the subject of many kinetic studies. Several papers have been devoted to the elucidation of the mechanism of aliphatic and aromatic ketone oxidation reactions by various oxidants¹. However, 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol oxidation of cyclopentanone, cyclohexanone and 2-methylcyclohexanone has yet not been studied. It may be noted that 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol is a mild oxidant having low redox potential of +0.22 V at pH 7. Basford and Huenekens² employed this oxidant for some kinetic studies. Sinha and Mishra³ investigated the reaction path of the oxidation of a number of compounds containing SH group. The aforesaid studies led us to examine the mechanistic path of the oxidation of cyclopentanone, cyclohexanone and 2-methylcyclohexanone by 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol in aqueous alkaline medium.

Experimental

Cyclopentanone, cyclohexanone and 2-methylcyclohexanone (AnalaR) solutions were made in double-distilled water. The solution of 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol (B.D.H.) was prepared fresh in double-distilled water and standardised⁴. All other reagents (AnalaR) were prepared in double-distilled water.

Kinetics of oxidation of cycloketones were followed colorimetrically by measuring the depletion in the concentration of 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol with time using an Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer. The λ_{max} of 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol was at 620 nm in higher alkaline medium (pH \geq 10). Beer's law was found to be obeyed over the entire concentration range of the oxidant. Since

the concentration of the oxidant directly corresponds to the optical density hence the velocity constants were calculated with the help of the equation having a relation between velocity constant and optical density. The runs were made under N₂ atmosphere though it was observed that for the duration of the experiments described, its absence did not affect the rate.

Stoichiometry and products: The stoichiometry was determined analytically as well as spectrophotometrically. In the former case, the amount of indophenol consumed by ketone was determined while in the latter, amount of the dimer^{1,5} formed was determined employing the relationship, $D = \epsilon Ct$ at the wavelength of its maximum absorbance. The formation of the dimer has already been reported in the literature. The dimer formed could not be isolated in the present study due to some experimental difficulties. These experiments lead to a stoichiometry of 2 : 1 in accordance with equation (1).

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying indophenol concentration: The reaction velocity showed second order kinetics with respect to 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol for many-fold variation in the oxidation of cycloketones in aqueous alkaline medium (Table 1); KCl was added to maintain the ionic strength of the medium constant although it is a reaction between two organic molecules. This is also evident from the second order plots (Fig. 1). Table 1 shows that with increasing concentration of indophenol the rate constant values gradually decrease. Incidentally, this observation is similar to that made by earlier workers^{3,6} using this oxidant in the oxidation of different thio-alcohols and thio-acids.

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Fig. 1. Plots of $x/(a-x)$ vs time; temp. = 30° , $\mu = 0.15 M$: A (O) [Cyclopentanone] = $0.5 \times 10^{-2} M$, [Indophenol] = $0.20 \times 10^{-4} M$, [NaOH] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, [KCl] = $1.4 \times 10^{-1} M$; B (●) [Cyclohexanone] = $0.2 \times 10^{-2} M$, [Indophenol] = $0.20 \times 10^{-4} M$, [NaOH] = $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, [KCl] = $0.13 M$; C (⊙) [2-Methylcyclohexanone] = $0.2 \times 10^{-2} M$; [Indophenol] = $0.25 \times 10^{-4} M$, [NaOH] = $4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, [KCl] = $1.10 \times 10^{-1} M$.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF INDOPHENOL ON THE REACTION RATE

(A) Temp. = 30° , [Cyclopentanone] = $0.5 \times 10^{-2} M$, [NaOH] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, [KCl] = $1.4 \times 10^{-1} M$, $\mu = 0.15 M$						
[Indophenol] ($\times 10^4 M$)	0.20	0.25	0.40	0.50	1.00	
K_2 ($10^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$)	15.75	9.61	4.91	4.00	2.59	
(B) Temp. = 30° , [Cyclohexanone] = $0.2 \times 10^{-2} M$, [NaOH] = $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, [KCl] = $1.30 \times 10^{-1} M$, $\mu = 0.15 M$						
[Indophenol] ($\times 10^4 M$)	0.20	0.25	0.40	0.50	1.00	
K_2 ($\times 10^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$)	10.25	7.23	6.75	3.66	2.05	
(C) Temp. = 30° , [2-Methylcyclohexanone] = $0.20 \times 10^{-2} M$, [NaOH] = $4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, [KCl] = $1.1 \times 10^{-1} M$, $\mu = 1.15 M$						
[Indophenol] ($\times 10^4 M$)	0.20	0.25	0.40	0.50	1.00	
K_2 ($\times 10^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$)	8.16	5.60	3.67	3.33	2.28	

Effect of varying cycloketone concentration: The plots of the rate constant values vs concentration of cycloketones (Fig. 2), which passed through the origin, led to the conclusion that the order with respect to cycloketone is unity.

Effect of varying hydroxide ion concentration: The order with respect to hydroxide ion concentra-

tion was found to be unity in case of all the three cycloketones (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Plots of k_2 vs concentration [cycloketone]; temp. = 30° , [Indophenol] = $0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\mu = 0.15 M$: A (O) [Cyclopentanone], [NaOH] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, [KCl] = $1.4 \times 10^{-1} M$; B (●) [Cyclohexanone], [NaOH] = $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, [KCl] = $0.13 M$; C (⊙) [2-Methylcyclohexanone], [NaOH] = $4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, [KCl] = $1.1 \times 10^{-1} M$.

Fig. 3. Plots of k_2 vs $[OH^-]$; temp. = 30° , [Indophenol] = $0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\mu = 0.15 M$: A (O) [Cyclopentanone] = $0.5 \times 10^{-2} M$, B (●) [Cyclohexanone] = $0.2 \times 10^{-2} M$, C (⊙) [2-Methylcyclohexanone] = $0.20 \times 10^{-2} M$.

Effect of varying neutral salt concentration: The addition of neutral salt (KCl) did not produce any change in the rate over a wide concentration range.

Effect of varying temperature : Arrhenius equation was found to be applicable and from the slope of the Arrhenius plot and by using Eyring equation, the different thermodynamic parameters were obtained (Table 2).

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF CYCLOPENTANONE, CYCLOHEXANONE AND 2-METHYLCYCLOHEXANONE BY 2,6-DICHLOROPHENOL INDOPHENOL IN AQUEOUS ALKALINE MEDIUM

	Cyclo-pentanone	Cyclo-hexanone	2-Methylcyclo-hexanone
$k_1 (\times 10^6)$	8.04	9.02	4.10
$\Delta E^\ddagger (\times 10^{-3} \text{ J mol}^{-1})$	57.49	64.65	64.48
$\Delta S^\ddagger (\times 10^{-4} \text{ KJ mol}^{-1})$	-16.14	-13.68	-14.39
$\Delta F^\ddagger (\times 10^{-4} \text{ J mol}^{-1})$	10.64	10.61	10.81

Mechanism : 2,6-Dichlorophenol indophenol has a quinoid structure as a part of its overall structure. It has its pH=5.7. Its structure shows the equilibrium,

In alkaline medium species II plays the role of oxidant. The complete reduction of one molecule of species would lead to the formation of leucodye (III),

In the following discussion species II is denoted by In, I by HIn and III by InH₂ or HInH₂ as the case may be.

As regards the role of hydroxide ion, it participates in the reaction in two ways. Firstly and mainly it is used up in the enolisation of cycloketone⁷. Secondly, in presence of hydroxide ion the quinonoid structure of indophenol converts into the following electronic form,

In the light of the results obtained above, the following reaction mechanism is proposed.

In the above scheme InH is a free radical with its unpaired electron present of the nitrogen atom in the indophenol molecules. The reaction is thus shown to proceed via free radical mechanism. This appears to be a correct postulation as is evidenced by the ability of the system to initiate the polymerisation of vinyl acetate.

According to the above scheme the rate of disappearance of indophenol is given by the expression,

$$-\frac{d[\text{In}]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{Complex}]_1 [\text{In}] \quad (2)$$

The formation of (Complex)₁ will be given by steps (II) and (III) of the proposed reaction scheme.

$$\frac{d[\text{Complex}]_1}{dt} = k_1 [\text{In}][\text{enolate}] - k_1[\text{complex}]_1 - k_2[\text{complex}][\text{In}] \quad (3)$$

With the help of equation (3) the final rate law can be given in terms of the decreasing concentration of indophenol as

$$\frac{d[\text{In}]}{dt} = \frac{kk_1k_2[\text{cycloketone}][\text{OH}][\text{In}]^2}{k_{-1} + k_2[\text{In}]} \quad (4)$$

The rate law thus explains the first order kinetics with respect to the cycloketone as well as to the hydroxide ion and second order kinetics with respect to 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol provided the value of $k_2[\text{In}]$ is small as compared to k_{-1} . This will be so because the reaction between indophenol and (Complex)₁ will be quite slow as compared to the disproportionation of (Complex)₁. Hence the inequality $k_{-1} \gg k_2[\text{In}]$ would hold and under such conditions equation (4) would reduce to

$$-\frac{d[\text{In}]}{dt} = \frac{kk_1k_2[\text{In}]^2[\text{cycloketone}][\text{OH}]^-}{k_{-1}} \quad (5)$$

or,

$$-\frac{d[\text{In}]}{dt} = K[\text{In}]^2[\text{Cycloketone}][\text{OH}] \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where, } K = \frac{kk_1k_2}{k_{-1}}$$

The proposed mechanism satisfactorily explains all the kinetic features except the retarding trend of the reaction rate with the increase of the initial 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol concentration. It is reported⁸ that in alkaline medium cycloketone

molecule which exists mainly in enolic structure, forms complex with the quinonoid ring of 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol. This type of species is expected to be relatively inert as compared to indophenol and hence retardation would occur with the increase of indophenol concentration. Similar results have already been reported by previous workers and our results further confirm this nature. However further study is needed by fast reaction kinetics.

The formation of diketone¹ has been reported during oxidation of ketones by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III). Similarly other workers⁵ also reported the formation of diketone during the oxidation reactions.

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